

Paper 8

INFORMATION ASSURANCE: EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM AT BACHELORS LEVEL—AN INTERNATIONAL LOOK

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Abstract

Security is become an important name these days for different reasons. Today organizations and institutions are engaged in information affairs and in which IT Components become important and valuable. Worldwide manpower requirement in this field is highly solicited, different educational institutions viz. colleges, universities, technical institutions are doing well in this context. There are different areas closely related with the Information Assurance such as Cyber Security, Information Security, IT Security, Computer Security etc. Information Assurance is a broader version of IT Security which talks and deals with both manual and computational security related affairs. Information Assurance moreover comes with the topics in policy designing for healthy information systems designing and development. The framework, guidelines for sustainable information systems designing is also part of Information Assurance. Initially different universities have been started Information Assurance program at Doctoral level and in recent past apart from Masters degrees few have started Bachelors as well. This paper is highlighted the basics of Information Assurance and mainly the available programs of Information Assurance at Bachelors degree level. Paper mentioned the emerging areas and topic of interest as well. It is noted that few universities offers the areas as a full-fledged manner and few as a specialization within a broader domain.

Keywords: Information Assurance, IT Security, Security Education, Information Privacy, Educational Development, Information Science, BS Information Assurance, Cyber Security

1.Introduction

Information Security is a valuable name in the field of Information Science and Technology; there are different Securities fall within this domain viz. IT security, Network security, Database security, Web security including latest and emerging Mobile and Cloud Security. Information Assurance is responsible for implementing and managing and various contents viz. information, data, and knowledge in different including manual and computational. Technological solutions and managerial solution to information are the core of Information Assurance [1], [5]. Information Assurance internationally started by many universities as

short term and long term program. There are various basics areas covered directly under the Information Assurance program viz. *Information and Computing, Managing Information in Organizations, Information and Society, Technology in Organizations and institutions, Information Organization and management including Information Policy etc.*

There are different nomenclatures available of this field and these are depicted in next section. Information Assurance as a broad and interdisciplinary field needs knowledge of various techno-managerial areas [12], [17] viz.—

- Communication Strategies for the IT & Security Professionals
- Enterprise Security Architecture
- Ethics for IT & Security Professionals
- Business Goals for the IT and Security Professionals
- Risk Assessment and Prevention
- Enterprise Tools, Concepts and Processes
- Governance, Quality, Compliance and Ethics
- Security Management [4], [6], [11].

Apart from these kind of techno-managerial areas; Information Assurance professionals should have knowledge in core technologies if they are interested to work in technology segment and among these few important are depicted in the section of ‘**Analysis of the Programs and Challenges**’

2.Objective and Agenda

This is a conceptual paper and theoretical in nature, the following are the core objective of the paper—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance including its stakeholders and origin in brief manner.
- To learn about the importance of the Information Assurance in basic and common sense.
- To know about the allied and related branches of Information Assurance with reference to educational programs available internationally on this domain.
- To learn about the Bachelors degree available on this areas with both fullfledged degrees and specialization based degrees.
- To learn about the focus and curriculums nature of such program for solving industrial problems.
- To find out the challenges, issues related to the Information Assurance in brief manner.

3.Information Assurance and Similar Educational Programs

Information Assurance is a latest and most emerging domain of security lies on technological policy sciences [2], [3], [7]. Among the other areas, few important are include Information Security, IT Security, Cyber Security, Computer Security, Cyber Forensic & Cryptography etc.

Information Assurance combines with both technological and manual information security related areas and fall under the interdisciplinary approaches and thus following merged nomenclature are also popular and available for the field viz.—

- Information and Cyber Security
- Information Assurance and Security
- IT Security and Information Assurance
- Information Assurance and IT Management
- Information Technology Management and Privacy etc.

Most of these type of programs are also available in different levels in many countries. The most common degree is Masters, among the leading universities; few are depicted in following table: 1.

Table: 1-Depicted few universities offers Masters in Information Assurance internationally

Sl. No.	Institute/ University	Name of the Program	Country
1	Davenport University	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (2 Years)	USA
2	Nova South Eastern University	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (1 Year)	USA
3	Sam Houston University	MS Information Assurance & Security (1 Year)	USA
4	Florida Institute of Technology	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (1 Year)	USA
5	Oklahoma State University	MS Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
6	CAPELLA University	MS Information Assurance & Cyber Security (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
7	Western Governors University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
8	Johnson & Wales University	MS Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
9	FAIRLEIGH DICKINSON University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
10	King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals	MS Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	UAE
11	Southern Utah University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA
12	Southern Utah University	MS Cyber Security & Information Assurance (No Time Frame Declared)	USA

Though few universities have started Information Assurance Doctoral program leading to traditional PhDs and other professional Doctorates. Table: 2 listed few universities in this regard.

Table: 2- Few universities offers Doctoral programs in IA or tagged nomenclature

Universities
Northeastern University
The University of Dallas, Texas
Capella University
The State University of New York
The University of Maryland
Colorado Technical University
University of Fairfax

It is worthy to note that most of these universities includes lot of Coursework including theories and practice in the Doctoral level program. And most of these are both Policy and Technology focused Security courses [8], [9], [12].

4.Information Assurance Program at Bachelors Level: A Case

Information Assurance is broader field and thus many universities have started Bachelors Degree in the field. However, universities are keeps both technological and managerial courses in the curricula. For this study general Search Strategy plays a leading role and total 22 results were considered to find out the BS/ BSc Program in Information Assurance or in similar nomenclature. Here it is important to note that, program without the term “Information Assurance” was not considered. As per the study following three universities noted with the Information Assurance nomenclature. Table: 3 is depicted the list of universities including the courses in detail (Source: URL of the Program).

Table: 2- Few universities offers Doctoral programs in IA or tagged nomenclature

Programs and Universities	Curriculum Focus on the Security
BS-IT (Information Assurance and Cyber Security), offered by the Capella University, United State. 180 Credit	<p>General Education (45 Credit) Communication Humanities Natural Sciences & Mathematics Social Sciences</p> <p>Core Courses (51 Credit) IT Concepts &Practice Communication Strategies for the IT Professionals Introduction to the Database Systems Introduction to Programming with Java Introduction to the Network Technology Ethics for IT Professionals</p>

	<p>Introduction to the Web Development Introduction to the Java Script Business Goals for the IT Professionals User Experience and Interaction Design Hardware & Operating Systems System Administration Software Architecture Intermediate Java Programming Network Architecture Principles of Project Management</p> <p>Specialization (51 Quarter Credit) Introduction to the Programming Cyber Defense & Countermeasures Cyber Attacks & Ethical Hacking Organizational Security Computer Forensic Security Management & Policies Python Scripting Operating Systems and Application Security System Assurance Security Electives (27 Quarter Credit) Capstone Project (06 Credit)</p>
<p>BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the City University of Seattle, United State.</p> <p>180 Credit</p>	<p>Basics for the Degree Fundamentals of Accounting Introduction to Web Design Any Two Research Methods & Practice Justice and Ethics Criminal Procedural Law Principle of Micro Economics</p> <p>Governance, Risk Management, and Compliance Core (45 Credits) Cybercrime, Technology, and Social Change (5) Cyber and Surveillance Law and Governance (5) Investigation of Cyber Crime (5) Applied Criminology and Crime Prevention (5) Enterprise Risk Management (5)</p>

	<p>Homeland Security and Espionage (5) Policy and Audits (5) IT Compliance (5) Investigation of Business Crimes (5) Or Risk Assessment and Prevention (5)</p> <p>Cybersecurity Technology Core (40 Credits)</p> <p>Network Communications Basics (5) Network Security (5) Data Management Communications and Networking (5) Internet Technologies (5) Information Systems (5) Information Security (5) Tools and Techniques (5) Computer Science I: C++ (5) Or Programming with Python (5)</p> <p>Required Electives (10 Credits) Any Two</p> <p>Legal Issues in the Workplace Operations Management (5) Fundamentals of Criminology (5) Investigation of Business Crimes* (5) Organizational and White-Collar Crime (5) Communicating Crisis, Emergency, and Social Change (5) Systems Analysis and Design (5)</p> <p>Capstone (5 Credits) Bureaupathology (5)</p>
<p>BS-Cyber Security and Information Assurance, offered by the University of Michigan-Dearborn, United State.</p> <p>106 Credit</p>	<p>Cyber Security and Information Assurance (CIA) Core</p> <p>Computer Science 1 Computer Science 2 Computer Organization and Assembly Language Data Structure and Algorithm Analysis Software Engineering 1 Database Management Systems</p>

	<p>Computer Networks Web Technology Operating Systems Design Seminar 1 Design Seminar 2</p> <p>Concentration <i>(Cyber Forensic/Cyber Security & Privacy)</i> Cyber Forensic Specialization Digital Forensic-1 Digital Forensic-2 Introduction to Computer and Network Security Or Multimedia Forensic Or Digital Content Protection Criminology Digital Evidence Forensic Evidence Intel and Homeland Security Or Cyber Crime Cyber Security & Privacy Specialization Computer Security Wireless and Mobile Computer Security Data Security & Privacy Intel & Homeland Security Digital Content Protection And one 6 Credit Elective</p>
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It is worthy to note that among the areas related with the Information Assurance most common and merged nomenclature was Cyber Security, and all these result showing universities are belongs to US based.

5. Analysis of the Programs and Challenges

The listed universities have followed the basic nature of Information Assurance and thus listed both technological and managerial courses of security. Among the Technological Security areas few important—

- Network Security & Privacy or Secure Networks and Communications
- Database Security & Privacy or Secure Database and Information Systems

- Web Security or Secure Website
- Internet Security or Secure Internet
- Secure Software Coding or Secure Software Engineering
- Secure Multimedia Systems
- Secure Contents and Privacy
- Hacking and Countermeasures
- Digital Forensic
- Secure Server and System Administration
- Secure Operating Systems

The most universities offers program with basics of IT and then concentration or Major on the Information Assurance area. Homeland security is an emerging area of Information Security as well.

6. Conclusion with Suggestions

Technological Security related to the Information products, services are the core of Information Assurance. Various components and their security concerns are the core of this. Similarly, other hand managerial security also important and as a result most of these universities focused on this and various courses listed within this viz. Cybercrime, Technology, and Social Change, Cyber and Surveillance Law and Governance, Investigation of Cyber Crime, Applied Criminology and Crime Prevention, Enterprise Risk Management, Homeland Security and Espionage, Policy and Audits of Security, IT Compliance, Investigation of Business Crimes, Risk Assessment and Prevention etc [13], [15], [16]. But it is worthy to note that the areas of manual Content security may also included which are absent and among these few promising may be fundamentals of Information Management, Documentations and Information Sources, Information Management etc. Few emerging technologies may also included viz. Mobile Security, Cloud Security, IoT Security etc for more better results among the products.

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